

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16414243

The Weibull Exponentiated Fréchet distribution: Properties and Applications to Engineering and Environmental Data

¹Oseghale O. Innocent, ²Laoye V. Eshomomoh & ³Oyebimpe Emmanuel Adeniji

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics,
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

^{2,3}Department of Statistics,
University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

innocentoseghale@gmail.com¹, laoyevictoriae@gmail.com², emmanuel4444real@yahoo.com³

ABSTRACT

In recent decades, many researchers have worked to model phenomena in which the distribution of data presents more or less heavy tails. With this concept, several generalizations or extensions of the Fréchet distribution have been proposed and studied. In this work, we made attempt to develop a hybrid distribution by convoluting the functionalities of the Exponentiated Fréchet and Weibull family of distributions, called the Weibull Exponentiated Fréchet (WEF) distribution. The WEF distribution has the features of having five parameters, a lower bounded support, and very flexible distributional functions, including a decreasing or unimodal probability density function and an increasing, decreasing, or upside-down bathtub hazard rate function. In addition, it benefits from the treatable statistical properties of moments and quantiles. The statistical applicability of the WEF model is highlighted, with simulations carried out. Two lifetime data sets are also used to illustrate the practical applications. In particular, results are compared with the sub-models, and it is observed that the WEF model fits better.

Keywords: Unimodal probability density function, moments, hazard rate function, Weibull Exponentiated Fréchet distribution.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

A flexible model for the analysis of lifetime data sets is often attractive and dependable to the researchers. Fréchet distribution is of interest due to its flexibility and simplicity. In recent decades, many continuous univariate distributions have been developed but various data sets from reliability, insurance, seismology, finance, climatology, biomedical sciences and other areas do not follow these distributions. Therefore, the development of extended and generalized distributions and their applications to real life problems in these areas is of great interest of the day. The extended and generalized distributions are obtained by the introduction of some transformation or addition of one or more parameters to the baseline distribution which sometimes may be as a result of convolution of two distributions. These new developed distributions provide better fit to data than the sub and competing models.

Recently, attempts have been made to define new families of probability distributions that extend well-known families of distributions and at the same time provide great flexibility in modeling data in practice. One such class of distributions is generated from the beta random variable. This class of generalized distributions has been receiving considerable attention over the last decade. One may refer to Eugene et al. (2002) who developed and studied the Beta generated family of distribution, Marshall and Olkin generalized family distribution by Marshall and Olkin (1997). Beta- and generalized gamma-generated distributions by Zografos and Balakrishnan (2008). A new family of generalized distributions developed by Cordeiro and deCastro (2011). exponentiated generalized class of distributions by Cordeiro et al. (2013). The Weibull-G family of probability distributions by Bourguignon et al. (2014), the logistic-X family by Tahir et al. (2016). The odd Chen generator of distributions by Eliwa et al. (2020). Out of the several families of distributions, of interest to us in this study is the Weibull- generated (W-G) family of distributions presented by Bourguignon et al. (2014). A generalized class of distribution called Weibull-generated (W-G) family of distributions was developed by Bourguignon et al. (2014). The CDF of the W-G is defined as follows,

$$F(x; \theta, \omega, \zeta) = \int_0^{\frac{G(x, \zeta)}{\bar{G}(x; \zeta)}} \alpha \beta t^{\beta-1} e^{-\alpha t^\beta} dt = 1 - e^{-\theta \left[\frac{G(x, \zeta)}{\bar{G}(x; \zeta)} \right]^\omega}, \quad (1)$$

A random variable X with pdf (1) is denoted by $X \sim \text{Weibull-G}(\theta, \omega, \zeta)$. If $\omega = 1$, it corresponds to the exponential generator. Here, $G(x, \zeta)$ is the CDF of the baseline with parameter vector ζ and $\bar{G}(x; \zeta) = 1 - G(x, \zeta)$ Based on W-G family, in particular, Weibull Fréchet by Affify et al. (2016), Weibull Inverse Lomax distribution by Amal and Rokaya (2019), among many others.

2.0 Exponentiated Fréchet distribution

According to Nadarajah and Kotz (2003), a random variable X follows an Exponentiated Fréchet (EF), if the Cumulative distribution (CDF) distribution is given by

$$G(x) = 1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^\rho, \quad x > 0; \quad \alpha, \zeta, \rho > 0 \quad (2)$$

and the corresponding density function (PDF) to (2) is

$$g(x) = \alpha \zeta x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{\rho-1}, \quad x > 0; \quad \alpha, \zeta, \rho > 0. \quad (3)$$

Where α is a scale parameter, ζ and ρ are shape parameters. An expression for the survival and the hazard function of EF distribution is, respectively, given as

$$S(x) = 1 - G(x) = \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^\rho \quad (4)$$

and

$$h(x) = \zeta x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

the EF distribution has many real-life applications including ranging accelerated life testing, earthquakes measurement, floods, horse racing, queues in banks, sea currents, wind speeds, rainfall and track race records among many others. For further studies on EF distribution see Nadarajah and Kotz (2003). Using the generalization given in (1), the CDF of the Weibull Exponentiated Fréchet distribution can be obtained by plugging (2) and (3) in (1) as

$$F_{WEF}(x; \alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta, \omega) = 1 - e^{\left\{-\theta \left[\left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^{\omega}\right\}}, \quad x > 0; \alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta, \omega > 0 \quad (6)$$

The associated PDF to (6) is given by

$$f_{WEF}(x; \alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta, \omega) = \alpha \zeta \rho \theta \omega x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{-(\rho\omega+1)} \left(1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{\rho}\right)^{\omega-1},$$

$$\times e^{\left\{-\theta \left[\left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^{\omega}\right\}}. \quad x > 0; \alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta, \omega > 0 \quad (7)$$

Where α is a scale parameter ζ, θ, ω and ρ are shape parameters A random variable X with density function (7) will be denoted by $X \sim WEF(x; \phi)$. It contains the following new special models:

- For $\rho = 1$, Weibull Fréchet (WF) distribution
- For $\alpha = 1$, Weibull Exponentiated Inverse Exponential (WEIE) distribution
- For $\rho = \zeta = 1$, Weibull Inverse Exponential (WIE) distribution
- For $\alpha = \rho = 1$, Weibull Inverted Weibull (WIW) distribution
- For $\theta = \omega = 1$, Exponentiated Fréchet (EF) distribution.
- For $\rho = \theta = \omega = 1$, Fréchet (F) distribution.
- For $\alpha = \theta = \omega = 1$, Exponentiated Inverted Weibull (EIW) distribution.
- For $\zeta = \theta = \omega = 1$, Exponentiated Inverse Exponential (EIE) distribution.
- For $\rho = \zeta = \theta = \omega = 1$, Inverse Exponential (IE) distribution.
- For $\alpha = \rho = \theta = \omega = 1$, Inverted Weibull (IW) distribution

An expression for the reliability and hazard rate function (hrf) of X are respectively, given as follows:

$$R(x; \phi) = e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega}, \quad (8)$$

$$h(x; \phi) = \alpha \zeta \rho \theta \omega x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{-(\rho\omega+1)} \left(1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^\rho \right)^{\omega-1}, \quad (9)$$

In addition, the reversed, hrf ($r(x; \phi)$) and cumulative hrf ($H(x; \phi)$) of X are obtained as follows

$$r(x; \phi) = \alpha \zeta \rho \theta \omega x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{-(\rho\omega+1)} \left(1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^\rho \right)^{\omega-1} \\ \times e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega} \left[1 - e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega} \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

and,

$$H(x; \phi) = \log R(x; \phi) = -\left\{ \theta \left[\left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega \right\}. \quad (11)$$

Plots of the CDF, PDF and hazard rate function of the **WEF** distribution are, respectively, given in Figures 1 and 2, and 3 for different hypothetical values of parameters of the distribution. As seen the shapes of PDF assumed different forms as right skewed, and unimodal. Also, it is clear from Figure 2 that the shapes of the hrf are J-shaped, reversed J- shaped, decreasing and increasing at some selected values of parameters.

Figure 1.0. Graph of the distribution function of the WEF distribution

Figure 2.0. Graph of the density function of the WEF distribution

Figure 3.0. Graph of the hazard function of the WEF distribution

2.1 Important representation

In this subsection, an important tool for the expansion of the PDF and CDF for *WEF* is provided. From the generalized binomial series given by

$$(1 + v)^{-b} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (-1)^i \binom{b+i-1}{i} v^i \quad (12)$$

and

$$e^x = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^j}{j!} \quad (13)$$

For $|v| < 1$ and b is a positive real non-integer. Then, by applying the binomial theorem (12) and (13) in (7), the density function of *WEF* distribution becomes

$$f(x; \zeta) = \alpha \zeta \rho \omega \theta \sum_{i=j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{i+j} \frac{\theta^i}{i!} \binom{\omega(i+1)-1}{j} x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}}\right)^{-[\rho(\omega-j-1)+1]} \quad (14)$$

The expression given in (14), is the *EF* distribution with scale parameter α and shape parameters ζ and $\rho(\omega - j - 1)$. Further simplification gives

$$f(x; \zeta) = \alpha \zeta \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha(k+1)x^{-\zeta}} \quad (15)$$

where,

$$\mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} = \rho \theta \omega \sum_{i=j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{i+j} \frac{\theta^i}{i!} \binom{\omega(i+1)-1}{j} \quad (16)$$

(15) is the Fréchet distribution with shape parameter ζ and scale parameter $\alpha(k+1)$. Some of the properties of *WEF* distribution like the moments, incomplete moments, moments generating function and the characteristic function will be derived using (15).

2.2 Quantile function

The quantile function of X , where $X \sim WEF(x; \zeta)$ is obtained by inverting $X_q = F^{-1}(q)$ as

$$X_q = \left\{ -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{1}{\left(\left[-\frac{1}{\theta} \ln(1-u) \right]^{1/\omega} + 1 \right)} \right\}^{1/\rho} \right] \right\}^{-1/\zeta} \quad (17)$$

The expression given in (17) can be used for generating random numbers for the *WEF* distribution. The median ($X_{med.}$) and the upper quartiles (X_{up}) for the *WEF* distribution can be obtained by taken u to be 0.5 and 0.75 respectively as given by

$$X_{mean} = \left\{ -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{1}{\left(\left[-\frac{1}{\theta} \ln(0.5) \right]^{1/\omega} + 1 \right)} \right\}^{1/\rho} \right] \right\}^{-1/\zeta} \quad (18)$$

And

$$X_{up} = \left\{ -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{1}{\left(\left[-\frac{1}{\theta} \ln(0.25) \right]^{1/\omega} + 1 \right)} \right\}^{1/\rho} \right] \right\}^{-1/\zeta} \quad (19)$$

2.3 The Galton Skewness and Moors Kurtosis

The Galton skewness (S_{GS}) is used to describe the degree of the long tail (towards left if S_{GS} is less than 0 or right side if S_{GS} is greater than 0). According Galton (1883),

$$S_{GS} = \frac{Q_{6/8} - 2Q_{4/8} + Q_{2/8}}{Q_{6/8} - Q_{2/8}}$$

The Moors kurtosis (M_k) is used to describe the degree of tail heaviness (if M_k increases, the tail of the distribution becomes heavier. According to Moor (1988),

$$M_k = \frac{Q_{6/8} - Q_{5/8} + Q_{2/8} - Q_{1/8}}{Q_{6/8} - Q_{2/8}}$$

Where $Q(\cdot)$ represents the quantile function given in (18). Table 1.0 gives various numerical values for the Moor's kurtosis and the Galton's skewness for various values of the parameters ρ , θ , and ω , and for fixed values of $\alpha = 2.0$ and $\zeta = 4$.

Table 1.0 Lower, Middle, Upper quartiles, Skewness and Kurtosis of *WEF* distribution

ρ, θ, ω	$Q_{1/8}$	$Q_{2/8}$	$Q_{4/8}$	$Q_{5/8}$	$Q_{6/8}$	$Q_{7/8}$	S_{GS}	M_k
0.2,2,3	1.0191	1.0475	1.0829	1.0978	1.1130	1.1315	16.4519	0.9481
2,3,4	1.3327	1.3922	1.4695	1.5030	1.5382	1.5819	10.0062	0.9479
3,6,8	1.6539	1.7081	1.7754	1.8036	1.8327	1.868	14.1685	0.9519
3,5,10	1.7184	1.7654	1.8229	1.8466	1.8709	1.9004	17.1886	0.9555
0.1,0.1,0.1	1.100	1.4710	1.8929	2.0767	2.2734	2.5239	2.3025	1.0196
4,8,10	1.9451	2.0114	2.0932	2.1274	2.1625	2.2052	13.7704	0.9537
5,8,12	2.3068	2.3889	2.4901	2.5323	2.5757	2.6282	13.2468	0.9529
0.5,0.5,0.5	0.8767	0.9981	1.2280	1.3482	1.4822	1.6554	2.5869	0.8856
13,15,15	9.2871	10.0825	11.1107	11.5551	12.0216	12.6002	5.6693	0.9492

3. Statistical Properties

3.1 Moments and Incomplete Moments

The s^{th} moment of the *WEF* distribution about the origin is derived by using PDF (15) as follows:

If $X \sim WEF(\zeta)$, then the s^{th} moment of X can be obtained using

$$\mu'_s = E(X^s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^s f_{WEF}(x; \zeta) dx. \quad (20)$$

By substituting from (15) in (20), we get the s^{th} moment as follows

$$\mu'_s = E\alpha\zeta \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^{s-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha(k+1)x^{-\zeta}} dx. \quad (21)$$

Letting $y = \alpha(k+1)x^{-\zeta}$ in (21), finally, we derive an expression for the s^{th} moment of the *WEF* distribution as

$$\mu'_s = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{s/\zeta} (k+1)^{s/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - s/\zeta\right), s < \zeta \quad (22)$$

The mean of the *WEF* distribution can be derived by obtaining the first moment of *WEF* distribution.

This is done by taking $s = 1$ in (21) as follows

$$\mu'_1 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{s/\zeta} (k+1)^{1/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - 1/\zeta\right) \quad (23)$$

And the variance ($\sigma^2 = \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2$) given by

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{2/\zeta} (k+1)^{2/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - 2/\zeta\right) - \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{1/\zeta} (k+1)^{1/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - 1/\zeta\right) \right)^2 \quad (24)$$

The s^{th} central moment (μ_s) of X is given by

$$\mu_s = E(X - \mu'_1)^s = \sum_{m=0}^s (-1)^m (\mu'_1)^m \mu'_{s-m} \quad (25)$$

The skewness and kurtosis measures can be calculated from the central moments using an established relationship. To examine how the mean, μ'_1 , variance (σ^2), Coefficient of variation (CV), skewness (\mathcal{Z}_k) and kurtosis (\check{k}_u) change for various hypothetical values of parameters $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \omega$, and θ , numerical values are obtained. Table 1 contains the first six moments, μ'_1 , σ^2 , (CV), \mathcal{Z}_k and \check{k}_u of the *WEF* distribution for various values of parameters $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \omega$, and θ . It can be noticed that the *WEF* distribution can be used to model both the negatively or positively skewed data, and also, the *WEF* can be mesokurtic, platykurtic and Leptokurtic depending on the values of $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \omega$, and θ .

Table 2.0. First six moments, σ^2 , CV , κ_s , and κ_u of the *WEF* distribution

$\theta = 1.5$ and $\omega = 2.5$					
Moments	$\alpha = 1.5$ $\zeta = 0.5$ $\rho = 3.5$	$\alpha = 2.5$ $\zeta = 1.0$ $\rho = 5.5$	$\alpha = 3.5$ $\zeta = 0.5$ $\rho = 5.5$	$\rho = 3.0$ $\zeta = 0.2$ $\rho = 8.5$	$\rho = 1.3$ $\zeta = 0.2$ $\rho = 10.5$
μ'_1	0.6112	1.0516	2.2124	1.6229	0.1748
μ'_2	0.4123	1.1288	5.2655	3.4507	0.0744
μ'_3	0.3006	1.2338	13.2906	8.8209	0.0526
μ'_4	0.2336	1.3707	35.2266	25.8949	0.0531
μ'_5	0.1916	1.5451	97.3317	84.8816	0.0705
μ'_6	0.1646	1.7651	278.814	304.969	0.1167
σ^2	0.0387	0.0230	0.3708	0.8169	0.0438
CV	5.0810	6.6028	1.6422	1.1064	4.7757
κ_s	0.1784	-0.4284	0.0025	0.7710	2.6432
κ_u	2.7326	3.4851	2.7213	3.5263	14.1289

An expression for the incomplete moment of the *WEF* is derived as follows:

If $X \sim WEF(\zeta)$, then the s^{th} incomplete moment of X can be obtained using

$$\phi'_s = \int_{-\infty}^t x^s f_{WEF}(x; \zeta) dx. \tag{26}$$

By substituting from (15) in (26), we get the s^{th} moment as follows

$$\phi'_s = E\alpha\zeta \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \int_{-\infty}^t x^{s-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha(k+1)x^{-\zeta}} dx. \tag{27}$$

Letting $y = \alpha(k+1)x^{-\zeta}$ in (27), finally, we have

$$\phi'_s = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{s/\zeta} (k+1)^{s/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - s/\zeta; \alpha(k+1)t^{-\zeta}\right), s < \zeta \tag{28}$$

The first incomplete moment of the *WEF* distribution which is important tool in deriving the Lorenz and Bonferroni curves can be derived by obtaining the by taking $s = 1$ in (28) as follows

$$\phi_1' = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{1/\zeta} (k+1)^{1/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - 1/\zeta; \alpha(k+1)t^{-\zeta}\right), \quad (29)$$

3.2 Moment generating function and the characteristic functions of the WEF distribution

If $X \sim WEF(\zeta)$, then the moment generating function of X denoted by MGF (X) can be obtained using

$$MGF(X) = E(e^{tx}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{tx} f(x) dx \quad (30)$$

Recall from Taylor series expansion of the exponential function (e^{tx}) given by

$$e^{tx} = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{(tx)^s}{s!}, \quad E(e^{tx}) = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^s}{s!} E(X^s)$$

Therefore, the MGF (X) is given as

$$MGF(X) = \sum_{k=s=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^s}{s!} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{s/\zeta} (k+1)^{s/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - s/\zeta\right), \quad s < \zeta \quad (31)$$

In like manner we can derive the characteristic function based on s^{th} moment of the WEF as

$$\chi_x(t) = E(e^{itx}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{itx} f(x) dx, \quad (32)$$

Finally, we have

$$\chi_t(X) = \sum_{k=s=0}^{\infty} \frac{(it)^s}{s!} \mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta} \alpha^{s/\zeta} (k+1)^{s/\zeta-1} \Gamma\left(1 - s/\zeta\right), \quad s < \zeta \quad (33)$$

Where $\mathcal{H}_{i,j}^{\omega,\rho,\theta}$ is defined in equation (16)

3.3 Stress strength Reliability Parameter for WEF distribution

Suppose X_1 and X_2 represents an independent random variable that follows the WEF distribution containing sets of the following parameters $(\alpha, \zeta, \rho_1, \theta_1, \omega_1)$ and $(\alpha, \zeta, \rho_2, \theta_2, \omega_2)$, respectively. Then, the stress-strength reliability parameter is given by $R = P(X_2 < X_1)$.

$$\mathfrak{R} = P(X_2 < X_1) = \int_0^{\infty} f_1(x; \alpha, \zeta, \rho_1, \theta_1, \omega_1) F_2(x; \alpha, \zeta, \rho_2, \theta_2, \omega_2) dx \quad (25)$$

If $X \sim WEF(\phi)$, then \mathfrak{R} is given by

$$\mathfrak{R} = F_1(x; \zeta) - \alpha \zeta \rho_1 \theta_1 \omega_1 \sum_{i=j=k=l=m}^{\infty} \frac{\theta_2^i \theta_1^k}{i! k!} Z_q \binom{\omega_2 i}{j} \binom{\omega_1(1+j)-1}{l} (\alpha[m+1])^{-1} \quad (26)$$

where,

$$Z_q = \binom{\rho_1 k - (\rho_1 \omega_1(1+k) + 1)}{m}$$

3.4. Rényi Entropy Function and δ –Entropy

The entropy of a random variable provides a measure of the degree of uncertainty or randomness of a system. A larger the values of entropy, the greater uncertainty in the data (Rényi, 1961). The concept of entropy is very important in various applications such as in economics, science, engineering, and engineering. According to Rényi (1961) the entropy of a random variable X is defined by

$$I_{RY} = (1 - v)^{-1} \log \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f_{WEF}(x))^v \right], \quad (27)$$

for $v > 0$ and $v \neq 0$ The Rényi entropy of the *WEF* distribution is obtained by inserting the *PDF* (7) in (27), and solving numerically, we obtained an expression for the Renyi entropy of *WEF* as

$$I_{RY} = (1 - v)^{-1} \log \left[l_{m,p,q}^{\theta,v,\omega,\rho} \zeta^{v-1} (\alpha \rho \theta \omega)^v [\alpha(q+1)]^{-\left(\frac{v(\zeta+1)-1}{\zeta}\right)} \Gamma\left(\frac{v(\zeta+1)-1}{\zeta}\right) \right] \quad (28)$$

where,

$$l_{m,p,q}^{\theta,v,\omega,\rho} = \sum_{m=p=q=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{m+p+q} \frac{(\theta v)^m}{m!} \binom{v(\omega-1) + \omega m}{p} \binom{\rho(p-m) - v(\rho\omega + 1)}{q}$$

Immediately, it follows that the δ -entropy of X , say $M_{\delta}(X)$ is given by

$$M_{\delta}(X) = \frac{1}{1 - \delta} \log [1 - (1 - \delta) I_{RY}(X)] \quad (29)$$

Where an expression for $I_{\delta}(X)$ is given in (28).

3.5 Order statistics

A closed form expression for the PDF of the j^{th} order statistics of the *WEF* distribution is derived. Let $X_1 < X_2 < \dots, X_n$ denote the order statistics for a random sample x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n of size n from *WEF* distribution. It is established that, the j^{th} order statistic is defined by

$$f_{X(j)}(x; \zeta) = \frac{1}{B(j, n-j+1)} \sum_{l=0}^{n-j} (-1)^l \binom{n-j}{l} F(x; \zeta)^{j+l-1} f(x; \zeta) \tag{30}$$

Putting (6) and (7) in (30), we have

$$f_{X(j)}(x; \zeta) = \frac{\alpha \zeta \rho \omega \theta}{B(j, n-j+1)} \sum_{l=0}^{n-j} (-1)^l \binom{n-j}{l} \left(1 - e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega} \right)^{j+l-1} x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \\ \times \left(1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^\rho \right)^{\omega-1} \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{\rho[(\omega+1)+1]-1} e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega} \tag{31}$$

Applying Taylor series expansion given in (12) and (13), we have

$$\left(1 - e^{-\theta \left[(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}})^{-\rho} - 1 \right]^\omega} \right)^{j+l-1} = \mathcal{M}_{m,p}^{**} \left[1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{-\rho} \right]^{\omega(p+1)-1}$$

where

$$\mathcal{M}_{m,p}^{**} = \sum_{m=0}^{j+l-1} \sum_p^{\infty} \frac{(\theta(m+1))^p}{p!} (-1)^{m+\omega p} \binom{j+l-1}{m}$$

$$f_{X(j)}(x; \zeta) = \frac{\alpha \zeta \rho \omega \theta \mathcal{M}_{m,p}^{**}}{B(j, n-j+1)} \sum_{l=0}^{n-j} (-1)^l \binom{n-j}{l} x^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \left[1 - \left(1 - e^{-\alpha x^{-\zeta}} \right)^{-\rho} \right]^{\omega(p+1)-1}$$

(32)

The expression given in (32) shows that the j^{th} order statistics of the *WEF* distribution can be reduced to the Exponentiated Fréchet distribution with scale parameter α and shape parameters ρ and $\omega(p + 1)$.

4.0 Maximum Likelihood Estimates of the Parameters of WEF model

We now consider the WEF distribution as a statistical model, and we assume that the parameters $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$ and ω are unknown. We desire to give some details on the maximum likelihood estimates (MLEs) of the parameters. First, let n be a positive integer, X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be independent and identically distributed random variables drawn from the WEF distribution, and x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be corresponding observations. The likelihood function and log-likelihood ($l(\underline{x})$) functions are defined by

$$L(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n; \zeta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f_{WEF}(x_i; \zeta) \quad (33)$$

Then inserting (7) in (33), we have

$$L(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n; \zeta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \alpha \zeta \rho \theta \omega x_i^{-\zeta-1} e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} (D_i)^{-(\rho\omega+1)} (1 - D_i^\rho)^{\omega-1} e^{-\theta[D_i^{-\rho}-1]^\omega} \quad (34)$$

$$l(\underline{x}) = n \log(\alpha \zeta \rho \theta \omega) - (\zeta + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(x_i) - \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-\zeta} + (\omega + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 - D_i^\rho) - (\rho\omega + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log D_i - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n [D_i^{-\rho} - 1]^\omega \quad (35)$$

$$D_i = (1 - e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}})$$

respectively. Then, the MLEs of the parameters $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$ and ω , say $\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\zeta}, \hat{\rho}, \hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\omega}$, respectively, are defined by

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial \theta} = \frac{n}{\theta} - \sum_{i=1}^n [D_i^\rho - 1]^\omega \quad (36)$$

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial \omega} = \frac{n}{\omega} - \rho \sum_{i=1}^n \log D_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 - D_i^\rho) + \theta \sum_{i=1}^n [D_i^\rho - 1]^\omega \log[D_i^\rho - 1] \quad (37)$$

$$\frac{\partial l}{\partial \rho} = \frac{n}{\rho} - \omega \sum_{i=1}^n \log D_i - (\omega - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{D_i^\rho \log D_i}{(1 - D_i^\rho)} \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l}{\partial \alpha} = & \frac{n}{\alpha} - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-\zeta} + (\rho\omega + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^{-\zeta} e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}}}{D_i} + \rho(\omega - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x^{-\zeta} e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} D_i^\rho}{D_i [1 - D_i^\rho]} \\ & + \rho\theta\omega \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x^{-\zeta} e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} [D_i^{-\rho} - 1]^\omega (1 - e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}})}{D_i [1 - D_i^\rho]} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial l}{\partial \zeta} = & \frac{n}{\zeta} - \sum_{i=1}^n \log(x_i) + \alpha \sum_{i=1}^n x^{-\zeta} \log(x_i) - (\rho\omega + 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x^{-\zeta} \log(x_i) e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}}}{D_i} \\ & + \rho(\omega - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x^{-\zeta} \log(x_i) e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} D_i^\rho}{D_i [1 - D_i^\rho]} + \rho\theta\omega \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{[D_i^\rho - 1]^\omega x^{-\zeta} \log(x_i) e^{-\alpha x_i^{-\zeta}} D_i^\rho}{D_i [D_i^\rho - 1]} \end{aligned}$$

Setting $\frac{\partial l}{\partial \alpha}, \frac{\partial l}{\partial \zeta}, \frac{\partial l}{\partial \theta}, \frac{\partial l}{\partial \rho}, \frac{\partial l}{\partial \omega} = 0$, and solving then simultaneously gives the MLEs of $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$, and ω .

To obtain an approximate confidence intervals (CIs) for the parameters of *WEF* distribution, it is important to obtain an estimated values of the elements of variance covariance matrix *F* of the MLEs. The variance-covariance matrix *F* is estimated by the observed information matrix *F*,

Where

$$\hat{F} = \begin{pmatrix} J_{11} & J_{12} & J_{13} & J_{14} & J_{15} \\ J_{21} & J_{22} & J_{23} & J_{24} & J_{25} \\ J_{31} & J_{32} & J_{33} & J_{34} & J_{35} \\ J_{41} & J_{42} & J_{43} & J_{44} & J_{45} \\ J_{51} & J_{52} & J_{53} & J_{54} & J_{55} \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

where $J_{i,j}, i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ are the second partial derivatives of (35) with respect to $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$, and ω . They are the values of Fisher's information matrix analogous to $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$, and ω respectively. The diagonal element of the matrix in (40) gives the variances of the MLEs of $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta$, and ω , respectively. An approximate $100(1 - c)\%$ confidence interval for ϕ_p as

$$\hat{\phi}_p \pm Z_{v/2} \sqrt{\text{var}(\hat{\phi}_p)}$$

$\hat{\phi}_p = (\hat{\alpha}_p, \hat{\zeta}_p, \hat{\rho}_p, \hat{\theta}_p, \hat{\omega}_p)$, $Z_{v/2}$ is the upper $\left(\frac{v}{2}\right)$ 100th percentile of standard normal distribution.

4.1 Simulation Study

The validity of the Maximum likelihood estimation method used in obtaining the estimate of the parameters of the *WEF* distribution can be ascertained by conducting simulation study. The following steps are carried out:

- (1) By using (17), 1,000 samples of size n are obtained. The variates of the *MOEGE* distribution are developed using

$$X_q = \left\{ -\frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \left[1 - \left\{ \frac{1}{\left(\left[-\frac{1}{\theta} \ln(1-q) \right]^{1/\omega} + 1 \right)} \right\}^{1/\rho} \right] \right\}^{-1/\zeta}, \quad 0 < q < 1$$

- (2) The MLEs are computed for the samples, say $\hat{\phi}_p = (\hat{\alpha}_p, \hat{\zeta}_p, \hat{\rho}_p, \hat{\theta}_p, \hat{\omega}_p)$ for $p = 1, 2, \dots, 1,000$.
- (3) The mean square errors (MSEs) are calculated for the parameters of the *WEF* distribution. The above steps were repeated for $n = 50, 100, 150, 200, 250,$ and 300 with $\alpha = 1.3, \zeta = 0.5, \rho = 0.2, \theta = 0.3,$ and $\omega = 1.5$. Table 3 displays the absolute bias (AB) and standard error (SE) and the mean square error (MSEs) of $\alpha, \zeta, \rho, \theta,$ and ω . It can be concluded through Table 3.0 that MSEs of the parameters decayed toward zero as sample size increases as expected.

Table 3. AB, SE, and MSE for the *WEF* parameters

parameter	n	AB	SE	MSE
α	50	0.3783	0.0832	0.150
	100	0.2429	0.0680	0.09041
	150	0.290	0.0229	0.0846
	200	0.2815	0.0217	0.0797
	250	0.2666	0.0134	0.07125
	300	0.2371	0.0114	0.0564
ζ	50	1.0377	1.2479	2.6341
	100	0.9875	0.5806	1.3123
	150	0.8214	0.5908	1.0237
	200	0.0827	0.4953	0.8897
	250	0.7214	0.3487	0.6420
	300	0.3714	0.3807	0.2829
	50	0.1804	0.1164	0.0461
	100	0.127	0.0335	0.0173

ρ	150	0.105	0.030	0.0119
	200	0.1221	0.0224	0.0154
	250	0.0377	0.0529	0.0042
	300	0.0772	0.0180	0.0063
θ	50	0.6363	1.310	2.1210
	100	0.4450	0.8176	0.8665
	150	0.2592	0.6115	0.4411
	200	0.0780	0.2807	0.0849
	250	0.0765	0.2059	0.0482
	300	0.0673	0.1832	0.0381
ω	50	1.0231	0.7353	1.5874
	100	0.8489	0.8614	1.4626
	150	0.5816	0.8498	1.0604
	200	0.2263	0.8449	0.7651
	250	0.1564	0.7955	0.6573
	300	0.1147	0.6948	0.4959

5.0 Application of WEF Model to lifetime data sets.

In this section, we analyze two lifetime datasets: we demonstrate the usefulness and applicability of the WEF distribution using two real datasets in the field of environment, and engineering. The WEF model is compared to all its sub-models as given in the study. The first data set is the Aircraft Windshield data set by Murthy et al. (2004). The data consist of the failure times of 84 Aircraft Windshield. The data is mesokurtic, under-dispersed, and positively skewed as shown in Table 4.0. The Total Time on Test (TTT) and the Box plots are given in Figure 4.0, which shows that the data is positively skewed with an increasing failure rate.

Table 4.0 Exploratory data analysis for the wind shield data

Min.	Q1	median	Mean	Max.	variance	skewness	kurtosis
0.04	1.84	2.35	2.56	4.66	1.251	0.0995	2.3477

In order to compare the two distribution models, we considered criteria like the following:

- Negative twice the log-likelihood (-2ℓ): $-2\ell = -2\log(L)$;
- Akaike Information Criterion (AIC): $AIC = 2k - 2\log(L)$;
- Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (CAIC): $CAIC = AIC + \frac{2p^2 + 2p}{n - p - 1}$
- Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC): $BIC = \log(n)p - 2\log(L)$;

• Kolmogorov–Smirnov criterion (KS): $D = \max |F(x) - F_n(x)|$.

Here, p represents the number of parameters in the model, n the sample size, and ℓ the peak value of the log-likelihood function for the model in question. Models with lower values of the -2ℓ , AIC, CAIC, BIC, and KS are considered superior in terms of fit to the observed data.

Figure: Plots of Violin and TTT plot.

Table 5. MLEs and standard error (in braces) of the parameters of the models for wind shield data.

Model	α	Z	ρ	θ	w
WEF	0.9615 (0.5899)	0.6447 (0.3034)	8.4304 (3.7370)	0.0084 (0.0049)	0.5904 (0.4105)
WF	0.5483 (0.0962)	0.2987 (0.1389)	–(–)	0.0124 (0.0119)	6.2373 (2.70)
WIE	0.1565 (0.0350)	– (–)	– (–)	0.0037 (0.0010)	1.9683 (0.1404)
WIW	– (–)	0.1855 (0.0281)	– (–)	7.5781 (4.7349)	1.2465 (1.2465)
WEIE	– (–)	0.0181 0.0073	0.2401 (0.0354)	0.0065 (0.0031)	5.8976 (0.8550)
WEIW	– (–)	0.0608 (0.1342)	1.5435 (0.2087)	0.0431 (0.1532)	22.2551 (9.2376)
EF	5.1186 (0.4625)	0.4483 (0.0406)	25.7581 (9.1935)	– (–)	– (–)

<i>F</i>	1.3645 (0.1516)	0.8387 (0.0521)	– (–)	– (–)	– (–)
<i>EIW</i>	– (–)	0.8608 (0.0604)	1.0339 (0.1213)	– (–)	– (–)
<i>EIE</i>	1.4425 (0.2261)	– (–)	1.2518 (0.2179)	– (–)	– (–)
<i>IE</i>	1.2272 (0.1339)	– (–)	– (–)	– (–)	– (–)
<i>IW</i>	– (–)	0.8675 (0.0561)	– (–)	– (–)	– (–)

Table 6. Model selection criteria for wind shield data

<i>Model</i>	<i>–l</i>	<i>AIC</i>	<i>CAIC</i>	<i>HQIC</i>	<i>BIC</i>	<i>AD</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>CVM</i>
<i>WEF</i>	127.34	264.67	265.44	269.56	276.83	0.5014	0.070	0.0612
<i>WF</i>	131.93	271.85	272.36	275.76	281.36	0.7521	0.070	0.0773
<i>WIE</i>	134.89	275.77	276.07	278.71	283.07	1.0278	0.1137	0.1148
<i>WIW</i>	131.97	269.93	270.23	272.86	277.22	0.7620	0.0662	0.0782
<i>WEIE</i>	135.0	278.01	278.51	281.91	287.73	1.0699	0.1081	0.1194
<i>WEIW</i>	130.42	268.84	269.35	272.75	278.57	0.6239	0.0566	0.0627
<i>EF</i>	152.06	310.11	310.41	313.04	317.41	3.4178	0.1689	0.4979
<i>F</i>	194.54	393.07	393.22	393.03	397.94	9.6409	0.3128	1.7114
<i>EIW</i>	198.04	400.07	400.22	402.03	404.94	9.4280	0.3652	1.6667
<i>EIE</i>	198.52	401.19	401.19	403.0	405.91	10.7998	0.3045	1.9567
<i>IE</i>	199.36	400.72	400.77	401.70	403.15	11.1119	0.2935	2.0233
<i>IW</i>	198.07	398.15	398.20	399.12	400.58	9.5491	0.3548	1.6920

Based on the results obtained in Table 6.0, the *WEF* distribution is best fitted model for the wind shield data than the other sub-models considered in the study because the values of all information criteria of goodness of fit are significantly smaller in terms of $-2l$, AIC, BIC, CAIC, KS, CVM and AD.

The second data are an uncensored dataset from Murty, Xie, and Jiang (2004) used in the industry, representing the failure time (in weeks) of 50 components put into use at time. The data is positively skewed, over-dispersed, and leptokurtic. TTT plot in Figure 5.0 shows that the data an increasing failure rate.

Table 7.0 Exploratory data analysis for the failure time data

Min.	Q1	median	Mean	Max.	variance	Skewness	kurtosis
0.013	1.39	5.32	7.82	10.04	84.76	2.31	9.41

Figure 5.0 Violin and TTT plot for failure data.

Table 8. MLEs and standard error (in braces) of the parameters of the models for aircraft data.

<i>Model</i>	α	Z	ρ	θ	w
<i>WEF</i>	12.8114 (0.1699)	2.0251 (0.1465)	0.2233 (0.0706)	0.1031 (0.0178)	9.7043 (0.2094)
<i>WF</i>	1.0634 (0.8117)	4.4529 (1.0452)	-($-$)	0.0706 (0.0361)	0.3183 (0.0758)
<i>WIE</i>	0.4966 (0.6305)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)	0.0221 (0.0510)	1.5069 (0.2240)
<i>WIW</i>	- ($-$)	5.6982 (2.2227)	- ($-$)	0.0589 (0.0283)	0.2665 (0.1166)
<i>WEIE</i>	- ($-$)	7.1688 (4.1410)	0.2727 (0.1629)	0.2905 (0.1535)	10.0158 (8.4352)
<i>WEIW</i>	- ($-$)	6.7937 (0.1585)	0.0536 (0.0259)	0.1440 (0.0259)	1.5958 (0.2153)
<i>EF</i>	6.1589 (0.8956)	0.4503 (0.0882)	14.7745 (9.3868)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)
<i>F</i>	3.3313 (0.6276)	1.1186 (0.1348)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)
<i>EIW</i>	- ($-$)	4.1768 (0.878)	1.6216 (0.4203)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)
<i>EIE</i>	2.1541 (0.2315)	- ($-$)	0.3526 (0.1237)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)
<i>IE</i>	3.0789 (0.5204)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)
<i>IW</i>	- ($-$)	0.8348 (0.1192)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)	- ($-$)

Table 9. Model selection criteria for the failure data.

<i>Model</i>	$-2l$	<i>AIC</i>	<i>CAIC</i>	<i>HQIC</i>	<i>BIC</i>	<i>AD</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>CVM</i>
<i>WEF</i>	89.47	188.93	191.0	191.61	196.71	0.1861	0.0784	0.0267
<i>WF</i>	90.83	189.66	191.0	191.81	195.86	0.3801	0.1016	0.0656
<i>WIE</i>	92.05	190.11	190.88	191.72	194.77	0.3514	0.0909	0.3514
<i>WIW</i>	90.50	186.99	187.77	188.60	199.66	0.3497	0.0982	0.0605
<i>WEIE</i>	90.31	188.62	189.95	190.77	194.84	0.2377	0.0883	0.0372
<i>WEIW</i>	90.17	188.35	189.68	190.50	194.57	0.3022	0.0895	0.0514
<i>EF</i>	95.19	196.38	197.15	197.99	201.04	0.9829	0.1431	0.1714
<i>F</i>	101.01	206.02	206.39	207.09	209.13	2.0216	0.2054	0.3659
<i>EIW</i>	107.59	219.19	219.56	220.26	222.30	2.6036	0.3068	0.4751
<i>EIE</i>	99.74	203.48	203.85	206.58	204.55	1.8391	0.2168	0.3313
<i>IE</i>	101.41	204.83	204.95	205.36	206.38	1.9130	0.1994	0.3453
<i>IW</i>	116.29	234.57	234.69	235.11	236.13	1.6059	0.4435	0.2876

Based on the results obtained in Table 9.0, the *WEF* distribution is best fitted model than the other sub-models considered in the study because the values of all information criteria of goodness of fit are significantly smaller in terms of $-2l$, AIC, BIC, CAIC, KS, CVM and AD, except for *WEIW* with smaller AIC, BIC, CAIC, HQIC and higher KS, CVM, and AD.

6.0 Concluding Remarks

We have developed the WEF distribution along with its properties such as: descriptive measures based on the quantiles, moments, stress-strength reliability and Order statistics, Renyi and δ -entropies. Maximum Likelihood estimates are computed. The simulation study is performed using the quantile function of the WEF distribution to illustrate the performance of the MLEs. Goodness of fit shows that WEF distribution is a better fit. Applications of the WEF model to Wind shield and failure time's data are presented to demonstrate its flexibility and applicability in modeling lifetime data. We have shown that the WEF distribution is empirically better for modeling windshield and failure time's data.

References

- [1] Ahmed Z. Afify, Haitham M. Yousof, Gauss M. Cordeiro, Edwin M. M. Ortega and Zohdy M. Nofal (2016) The Weibull Fréchet distribution and its applications, Journal of Applied Statistics, 43:14, 2608-2626
- [2] Amal, S. H., Rokaya, E. M. (2019). Weibull Inverse Lomax Distribution. Pak.j.stat.oper.res. Vol. XV No. III 2019 pp587-603
- [3] Bourguignon, M., Silva, R. B., Cordeiro, and G. M. (2014). The Weibull-G family of probability distributions. Journal of data science, 2014; 12: 53–68.
- [4] Cordeiro, G. M., deCastro, M. (2011). A new family of generalized distributions. Journal of statistical computation and simulation, 2011; 81(7): 883–898.
- [5] Cordeiro, G. M., Ortega, E. M. M., and daCunha, D. C. C. (2013). The exponentiated generalized class of distributions. Journal of data science, 2013; 11: 1–27.
- [6] Eliwa, M. S., El-Morshedy, M., and Afiffy, A. Z. (2020). The odd Chen generator of distributions: Properties and estimation methods with applications in medicine and engineering. Journal of the national science foundation of Sri Lanka. 2020; To appear

- [7] Eugene, N., Lee, C., and Famoye, F. (2002). Beta-normal distribution and its applications. *Commun. Statist. Theory Methods* 31 (4), 497–512.
- [8] Galton, F. *Inquiries into Human Faculty and Its Development*; Macmillan and Company: London, UK, 1883. 18. Moors, J.J.A. A quantile alternative for kurtosis. *J. R. Stat. Soc. Ser. D* 1988, 37, 25–32.
- [9] Marshall, A. W., and Olkin, I. (1997). A new method for adding a parameter to a family of distributions with application to the exponential and Weibull families. *Biometrika*, 84: 641–652. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/84.3.641>.
- [10] Moors, J. J. (1988). A quantile alternative for kurtosis. *J. Royal Statist. Soc. D*, vol. 37, pp. 25-32.
- [11] Nadarajah, S. and Kotz, S. (2003) The Exponentiated Fréchet Distribution. *Interstat Electronic Journal*,14, 1-7.
- [12] Renyi, A. (1961). On measures of information and entropy. In *Proceedings of the Fourth Berkeley Symposium on Mathematics, Statistics, and Probability*. pp. 547-561.
- [13] Tahir, M. H., Cordeiro, G. M., Alzaatreh, A., Mansoor, and M., Zubair, M. (2016). The logistic-X family of distributions and its applications. *Communications in statistics-Theory and methods*; 45, 24: 7326–7349
- [14] Zografos, K., Balakrishnan, N. (2009). On families of beta- and generalized gamma-generated distributions and associated inference. *Statistical methodology*; 6: 344–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stamet.12.003>.